

NMR Spectroscopy of Oriented Molecules and its Applications to Inorganic Chemistry

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Principles and spectral details of nmr spectroscopy of oriented molecules are discussed. Differences in the appearance and the information-content between the spectra in isotropic and anisotropic media are described. Applications and limitations of the technique to inorganic chemistry are critically examined. A review of the work done in the area of structural studies of inorganic and organometallic compounds is presented.

THE technique of nmr spectroscopy of molecules oriented in anisotropic solvents such as those of nematic phases of liquid crystals¹ has been extensively applied to structural and conformational studies and the derived information has been summarised from time to time²⁻¹¹. A survey of the literature reveals that the application of the technique to inorganic and organometallic chemistry is relatively scarce probably due to relatively poor solubilities and the complexities of such systems in general. On the other hand, it is also evident from the available literature that the technique provides unique structural, conformational and spectral information. The availability of highly sensitive and sophisticated FT-NMR equipments with multi-nuclear capabilities ensures bright prospects of research in this area. It is, therefore, pertinent to summarise potential applications of the technique with particular reference to inorganic chemistry.

Principles and Experimentation

The theory of nmr spectra of oriented molecules is well known. It is similar to that of the spectra in isotropic media except that the spin Hamiltonian describing such spectra contains additional terms due to anisotropic interactions such as those involved in direct dipole-dipole couplings, chemical shift and indirect coupling anisotropies and quadrupole coupling constants. Consequently, the spectra provide additional information carried by the anisotropic interactions. For spin 1/2 nuclei, the line positions and the line intensities of the spectra in diamagnetic materials are, therefore, influenced by the chemical shift ($\nu_i - \nu_j$) including the contribution due to chemical shift anisotropy, indirect spin-spin couplings (J_{ij}), direct dipolar couplings (D_{ij}) and anisotropic contributions of indirect couplings ($D_{ij}^{p,q}$) where i and j are the two interacting nuclei. For H-H couplings, usually $D_{ij}^{p,q}$ is negligible and hence in such cases the obtainable additional information is that contained by the chemical shift anisotropy and the direct dipolar couplings. Since the direct dipolar couplings are inversely proportional to the cubes of the distances between the interacting nuclei, their determination

provides a precise method for the determination of molecular shapes - an information which cannot be obtained in the liquid phase directly by any other technique. The most convenient anisotropic medium is provided by the nematic phase of liquid crystals. If a molecule is dissolved in such a medium, it experiences orientational effects unlike in an isotropic medium where all orientations of the dissolved molecules are equally probable. The orientation of the molecules dissolved in liquid crystals is described by the order matrix $\{S\}$, the elements (S_{ij}) of which are given by equation (1):

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \langle 3 \cos^2 \theta_{ij} - 1 \rangle \cdot \frac{1}{2} (3 \cos^2 \alpha - 1) \quad \dots (1)$$

where θ_{ij} is the angle which the axis joining nuclei i and j makes with the liquid crystal optic axis and α is the angle between the direction of the magnetic field and the liquid crystal optic axis. For liquid crystals, $\alpha \neq 0^\circ$ or 90° depending upon the sign of the diamagnetic anisotropy of the liquid crystal and hence, the factor $\frac{1}{2}(3\cos^2\alpha - 1)$ in equation (1) is either 1 or $-\frac{1}{2}$.

If the axis connecting the nuclei i and j makes angles of θ_x , θ_y and θ_z with the axes x , y and z of the molecule-fixed Cartesian coordinate system, S_{ij} is written as

$$S_{ij} = \sum_{p,q} \cos \alpha_p \cdot \cos \alpha_q \cdot S_{pq} \quad \dots (2)$$

where p, q refer to the x, y, z axes of the coordinate system. The relationship between the degrees of order of various axes is implicit in equation (2).

The average molecular order is defined by a symmetric and traceless tensor with five independent elements. An appropriate selection of the molecule-fixed coordinate system reduces the number from 5 (for a system without a plane of symmetry) to 0 (for a case with cubic or spherical symmetry). If the molecule has a 3-fold or higher axis of symmetry, its selection as one of the axes leaves only one independent parameter. When there are two

perpendicular planes of symmetry each containing two axes of the Cartesian coordinate system, two independent values specify the molecular order. If the molecule possesses a single plane of symmetry containing two of the axes of the Cartesian coordinate system, 3-independent S-values define the molecular order.

The relation between the dipolar coupling (D_{ij}) and the order parameter is given by (3):

$$D_{ij} = -\frac{h\gamma_i\gamma_j}{4\pi^2} \cdot \frac{S_{ij}}{r_{ij}^3} \quad \dots (3)$$

where γ is the magnetogyric ratio and r_{ij} is the distance between nuclei i and j .

Relations between other anisotropic parameters and order parameters can be found in the literature in general. The chemical shift anisotropy ($\Delta\sigma_i$) of a nucleus in a 3-fold symmetry is given by (4):

$$\Delta\sigma_i = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{\sigma_{i\alpha}}{S_{\alpha\alpha}} \quad \dots (4)$$

where $\sigma_{i\alpha}$ is the chemical shift in the anisotropic medium with respect to that in the isotropic phase and $S_{\alpha\alpha}$ is the order parameter of the symmetry axis.

The methods of analysing the spectra in the anisotropic media are in general similar to those in the isotropic media. In fact, the Hamiltonian for an isotropic system transforms to that in an anisotropic medium if in the diagonal and the off-diagonal contributions to all the elements of the matrix, J_{ij} is replaced by $(J_{ij} + 2D_{ij})$ and $(J_{ij} - D_{ij})$ respectively and in the chemical shift term, $(1 - \sigma_i)$ is substituted for $(1 - \sigma_i - \sigma_{i\alpha})$ where σ_i and J_{ij} are the chemical shift and the indirect spin-spin couplings observed in the normal high resolution spectra in the isotropic media.

The proton spectra of molecules oriented in thermotropic liquid crystals are in general strongly coupled unless heteronuclei are involved in the interactions. Therefore, they are generally not amenable to first order analysis unlike most of the spectra in the isotropic media. Computer programmes are now available for the iterative analysis of the spectra. The programmes which are most commonly used to provide the best-fit spectral parameters, namely, the chemical shift, the direct and the indirect spin-spin couplings are referred as LAOCOONOR^{1,2} and LEQUOR^{1,3}. A typical spectrum is shown in Fig. 1.

Once the direct dipolar couplings are derived from the analysis of the spectra of oriented molecules, the next step is to interpret them in terms of molecular geometry and the order parameters. If the number of independent dipolar

Fig. 1. Proton magnetic resonance spectra of phosphacymantrene (π -phosphoryl manganese tricarbonyl) oriented in the nematic phase of Merck Phase IV. Solute concentration 3 mole per cent; temperature 27°; spectrometer frequency 90 MHz.

couplings equals the sum of the geometrical and the order parameters to be derived, one can solve simultaneous equations connecting the various parameters. If, however, the number of the independent dipolar couplings is less than the 'sum' as defined above, one cannot derive the complete geometry-information unless one makes certain assumptions on the molecular geometry; the minimum number of such assumptions equals the number by which the direct couplings fall short of the 'sum'. If the number exceeds the 'sum', an iterative procedure which computes the molecular geometry and the order by a weighted least-square-fit procedure is used. The computer program SHAPE^{1,4} is most commonly used for such a purpose.

Equation (3) connecting the dipolar couplings and the order parameters shows that if S_{ij} and r_{ij}^3 are changed by a constant factor, D_{ij} and hence the spectrum remains unchanged. Since S_{ij} has also to be determined from the nmr experiment and it needs the knowledge of an internuclear distance, nmr studies of oriented molecules provide molecular shapes, i.e., relative internuclear distances and the bond angles.

An illustrative example of the procedure for the determination of molecular geometry of phosphine is discussed in detail before a general review of the applications to inorganic chemistry is presented. Typical proton magnetic resonance spectrum of phosphine (PH_3) oriented in a nematic solvent is shown in Fig. 2. The spectrum consists of doublets of a triplet. The triplet with the intensity ratio of 1 : 2 : 1 arises from the HH dipolar coupling (D_{HH}). The spacing between the extreme lines corresponds to $6D_{HH}$. Each component of the triplet is further split into 1 : 1 intensity doublets due PH indirect and direct spin-spin couplings (J_{PH} and D_{PH} respectively) with spacings equal to $(J_{PH} + 2D_{PH})$. If J_{PH} is determined from the spectrum in the isotropic medium, the proton spectrum of phosphine provides D_{PH} and D_{HH} . The relation (5) between

Fig. 2. A typical proton magnetic resonance spectrum of phosphine oriented in a nematic solvent.

the dipolar couplings and the HPH bond angle (α) can then be used to determine the bond angle.

$$\frac{D_{PH}}{D_{HH}} = 16 \left(\frac{\gamma_P}{\gamma_H} \right) \sin^2 \alpha / 2 (2 \sin^2 \alpha / 2 - 1) \quad \dots (5)$$

Applications in Inorganic Chemistry

The applications in this direction have mainly been in the area of organometallic chemistry. The structure, conformation and chemical shift anisotropy have been investigated in a variety of organometallic compounds containing Cr, Mn, Fe, Ni, Ge, As, Se, Ru, Re, Cd, Sn, Sb, Te, W, Os, Pt and Hg as the metals. A large number of inorganic and organophosphorus compounds have also been examined. The bromine-pyridine charge transfer complex has also been studied¹⁵.

The available literature can be summarised under the following heads: the investigations on (1) π -complexes, (2) other metallic compounds, (3) phosphorus compounds and (4) weak molecular complexes.

(1) π -Complexes: The first inorganic complex to be studied was π -cyclobutadiene iron tricarbonyl¹⁶. The ring skeleton of the molecule is planar and the iron tricarbonyl moiety is involved in the formation of the π -complex with the π -electrons of the ring. The proton spectrum of the molecule can be analysed analytically, using the expressions reported in the literature or iteratively using the computer programme. An interpretation of the dipolar couplings indicates significant deviations from the square geometry of the ring skeleton. Therefore, the ring has a symmetry less than D_{4h} although the permutation group symmetry of the nuclear spins has a 4-fold axis. It may, probably, be due to the fact that the molecule interconverts rapidly between non-square equilibrium conformers. The angle between the symmetry and the Fe-C axes is estimated as $61 \pm 3^\circ$. In this case, it was not possible to determine the sign of the order parameter since the relative signs of the direct and the indirect couplings could not be determined. In π -benzene chromium tricarbonyl, it was clearly established¹⁷ that in the thermotropic

solvent formed by the mixture of N-(*p*-methoxybenzylidene)-*p*-amino- α -methyl cinnamic acid-*n*-propyl ester and *p*-(*p*-methoxyphenylazo)-phenyl-*n*-hexanoate, the molecule orients preferentially with the plane of the benzene ring along the direction perpendicular to the plane of the ring. Significant deviations from the regular hexagonal geometry of the benzene ring have been studied in π -benzene chromium tricarbonyl.

The 5-membered ring system, namely, π -cyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl¹⁸⁻²¹ and its methyl derivative²² have also been investigated. In the case of cyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl also, significant deviations from the regular pentagonal geometry of the ring system have been observed. The C-C bond distance between the carbonyl carbons in π -cyclopentadienyl iron tricarbonyl has been obtained as 2.78 Å. In π -methylcyclopentadienyl manganese tricarbonyl, the ring protons do not deviate significantly from the regular pentagonal arrangement. In addition, the rotation of the methyl group about the C-C bond is found to be hindered in a 3-fold potential due to the presence of the Mn(CO)₃ group.

In π -cyclopentadienyl nickel nitrosyl²³ and tricarbonyl tungsten hydride^{24,25}, the ring skeletons have been found to be regular pentagonal.

In *bis*(cyclopentadienyl) mercury²⁶, the spectrum is consistent with the σ -bonded structure if, and only if, there is some kind of averaging. The spectrum corresponds to symmetry achieved either by an exchange process or a bond-shift mechanism. The ratios of the interproton distances correspond to those expected for a regular pentagon.

The structure of the 1,3-butadiene moiety of 1,3-butadiene iron tricarbonyl which has been a puzzle for the past several years has been established to be non-planar²⁶. The distances between the *anti* protons from the remaining four protons is determined as 0.77 ± 0.06 Å. In π -allyl tetra carbonyl rhenium, the π -allyl group has been found to be non-planar²⁷.

A new application of nmr spectroscopy of oriented molecules has been discovered from the studies on phosphacymantrene and comparison of the results with geometrical data obtained for several 5 and 6 membered heteroaromatic molecules²⁸⁻³⁰. The results have led to the discovery of a new method for the determination of covalent and van der Waals radii. It is found that in such system, certain interproton distance ratios are related inversely to the covalent and the van der Waals radii. The covalent radii of O, N(H), C(H), S, P, Se, Te and As have thus been determined. Their values agree well with those reported in the literature and determined by other techniques.

(2) Other metallic compounds: A large number of compounds such as silane³¹, germane³¹, tetramethyltin³², methyl mercury halides^{33,34} and

nitrate³³, methyl tin chloride³⁰, methyl trichlorosilane and stannane³⁷, methyl germane³⁸, dimethylmercury³³, cadmium³⁹, selenium⁴⁰ and tellurium⁴⁰, 1,1,1-trifluoromethyl methyl mercury⁴¹, 2, 1, 3-benzoselenadiazole⁴², benzoselenenyl chloride⁴³, selenophene⁴⁴, benzoselenophene⁴⁵, 2,2'-biselenophene⁴⁶, selenophene-2-carbaldehyde⁴⁷ *bis* (ethane 1,2-dithiolato) nickel(IV)^{48,49}, trimethylene-methane-iron tricarbonyl, trihydro nona carbonyl methyl carbene tri osmium (or ruthenium)^{47,50,51} and ac-dichloro-b-ethylene pyridine ($-d_5$) platinum(II)⁵² have been studied.

Possible mechanism of distortions from tetrahedral symmetry in silane, germane and tetramethyl tin have been studied. In methyl mercury halides, the proton spectra including ^{13}C and ^{199}Hg have been investigated. The HCH bond angles of $110.00 \pm 0.04^\circ$, $110.10 \pm 0.03^\circ$ and $110.20 \pm 0.03^\circ$ have been determined for the chloro, the bromo and the iodo compounds respectively. The corresponding HHgC angles are 23.74° , 23.75° and 23.76° . A rapid halogen exchange has been observed in these compounds. The proton chemical shift anisotropy is 2.4, 2.6 and 2.8 ppm respectively for methyl mercury chloride, bromide and iodide. The mercury shielding anisotropy value of 5345 ppm has been obtained for methyl mercury bromide. In methyl mercury nitrate, the molecular geometries in the lyotropic and the thermotropic solvents are similar, indicating negligible solvent-solute interactions. The Sn-C-H bond angle of 107.4° has been obtained in methyl tin chloride. From the ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{29}Si , ^{117}Sn and ^{119}Sn spectra where M-C dipolar couplings were also observed, the molecular structures of methyl trichlorosilane and stannane have been determined.

In methyl germane, the relative conformations of the CH_3 and GeH_3 fragments are staggered or rotate freely about the Ge-C bond and the HCH bond angle is $108^\circ 48'$. Values of the HHgC angle and HCH bond angles in dimethyl mercury have been determined as 23.10° and 108.36° respectively. The angle between the H-Cd bond and the C_s -axis of symmetry and the HCH bond angle in dimethyl cadmium are determined as $23.04 \pm 0.13^\circ$ and 108.12° respectively. In contrast to dimethyl mercury and cadmium which have 3-fold axes of symmetry, dimethyl selenium and tellurium have only 2-fold symmetry axes. The proton spectra including the ^{13}C and the ^{77}Se (or ^{125}Te) satellites have been studied and the HCH bond angles in dimethyl selenium and tellurium have been determined as 110.142° and 110.799° respectively. The corresponding H-C-metal angles are 106.22° and 107.34° . In 1,1,1-trifluoro-methyl methyl mercury, precise determination of molecular geometry was difficult due to low degree of molecular order in the various solvents used and due to solvent and temperature dependence of the indirect spin-spin couplings.

The structures of 2,1,3-benzoselenadiazole, benzoselenenyl chloride and benzoselenophene have been

determined. Considerable bond fixation in the 6-membered ring has been observed in 2,1,3-benzoselenadiazole. In benzoselenenyl chloride, the phenyl ring geometry does not deviate significantly from the regular hexagonal arrangement of the protons. The Se-C bond length is estimated as 1.97 Å. The proton spectrum of 2,2'-biselenophene including ^{77}Se -H satellites shows that the molecule exists as an equilibrium between two twisted conformers with the transoid one being more abundant; the angle of twist is $25 \pm 5^\circ$. In selenophen-2-carbaldehyde, the dominant existence of the Se-O *cis*-conformer is indicated.

Bis (ethane-1,2-dithiolato)nickel has been studied at various temperatures. The results are consistent with the fact that the two organic ligands rotate with respect to each other. The HH distance ratios in trimethylene methane iron tricarbonyl have been determined. The M-H-M bond angles in trihydro-nonacarbonyl methyl carbene tri osmium (or ruthenium) have been estimated as 103° and 101° for the osmium and the ruthenium compounds respectively. The relative proton and platinum positions have been determined in ac-dichloro-b-ethylene pyridine (d_5) platinum(II) complex. It is found that the equilibrium structures have the pyridine ring inclined at an angle to the PtCl_2 plane with rapid reorientation between the symmetry related forms.

(3) *Phosphorus compounds*: A number of phosphorus compounds⁵³ such as phosphine⁵⁴, phosphorus trifluoride⁵⁵, phosphoryl fluoride⁵⁶, hexafluoro cyclophosphazene⁵⁷, hexachloro cyclophosphazene⁵⁷, octachloro cyclophosphazene⁵⁷, phosphorus sesquisulphide⁵⁸, phenylphosphine⁵⁹, cyclo-tetra phosphines⁶⁰, ^{13}C -triply labelled tribenzoyl phosphine⁶¹, trimethyl phosphine selenide⁶², difluorophosphine selenide⁶³, phenyl ester of dichloro phosphoric acid⁶⁴, methyl phosphonate⁶⁵, isotopically labelled (with ^{13}C and ^{15}N) *bis*(dichloro-phosphino) methylamine⁶⁶, trimethyl-phosphine, phosphine oxide, sulphide and selenide⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹, cyclo-tetra phosphanes⁷⁰ and hexaphenyl cyclohexaphosphine⁷¹ have been investigated.

The HPH bond angle in phosphine has been determined as $94.73 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and the ^1H and the ^{31}P chemical shift anisotropies are -7.5 and 955.5 ppm respectively. In phosphorus trifluoride, the FPF bond angle is 97.8° and the ^{19}F and ^{31}P chemical shift anisotropies are -49 ± 5 and 228 ± 2 ppm respectively. From studies of the ^{19}F and the ^{31}P nmr spectra at various temperatures in phosphonyl fluoride, the FPF bond angle and the ^{19}F and the ^{31}P -chemical shift anisotropies have been determined. The spectrum of octachlorocyclophosphazene corresponds to the D_{4h} -symmetry of the molecule. The ring-folding in cyclo-tetraphosphines has been estimated. The CPH bond angle in phenyl phosphine is determined as $96.4 \pm 1.0^\circ$. The chemical shift anisotropy in hexafluoro (and chloro) cyclophosphazene and phosphorus sesquisulphide have been determined.

From the proton decoupled ^{13}C and ^{31}P nmr spectra of ^{31}C -triple labelled tribenzoyl phosphine, the CPC bond angle and the ^{31}P -chemical shift anisotropy are determined as $95.9 \pm 0.2^\circ$ and 75 ± 15 ppm respectively. In the phenyl ester of dichlorophosphoric acid, the dihedral angle between the C-O-P and the phenyl planes is determined as 49° from the ^1H and the ^{31}P nmr spectra. The HCH bond angle in methyl phosphonate is determined as 109.6° . Nuclear magnetic double resonance studies of isotopically labelled (with ^{13}C and ^{15}N) bis(dichlorophosphino) methyl amine provide the P-N-P angle as $117.0 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and the distance ratio $r_{\text{PN}}/r_{\text{CH}}$ as 1.527.

The ^{13}C -chemical shift anisotropies in the $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{X}$ compounds are 0 ± 5 , 34 ± 10 , 8 ± 10 and 18 ± 10 ppm for X=P, PO, PS and PSe respectively and the corresponding C-P-C bond angles are 99.2 , 105.7 , 104.7 and 105.0° . The ring conformation of hexaphenyl cyclohexaphosphine determined from the nmr studies in the liquid phase agrees well with the X-ray data in the solid state. The 6-membered ring puckering angle is estimated to lie between 96.5 - 97° .

(4) *Weak molecular complexes*: The technique has also been applied to study charge transfer, hydrogen bonded and other weak molecular complexes. The charge transfer complex between pyridine and bromine is found to be linear such that the two bromines are on the C_2 -axis of symmetry¹⁵. The interproton distance ratios in the complex have been determined. The values are significantly different from those in pyridine. A trimethyltin-pyridine (d_5) complex has also been investigated^{16,72}. The configurational changes around the tin atoms have been observed as a result of the complex formation. The C-Sn-C bond angle in trimethyltin changes from 113.9° without pyridine to a value of 120° in presence of pyridine. The results are in agreement with 1:1 complex formation between trimethyltin chloride and pyridine. Dipolar couplings between the protons of trimethyltin chloride and the deuterons of pyridine were not observed implying a fast exchange between the bound and the free states.

Conclusion

It is seen that the technique of nmr spectroscopy of oriented molecules can be applied to a variety of structural and conformational problems in inorganic chemistry. The studies on the weak molecular complexes provide unique information in the liquid phase.

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